
Environmental Weathering: How Beach Sand and Sea Alter the Chemical Composition of Gloves and Mouth Masks

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Abstract

COVID-19 pandemic led to an unprecedented global demand for personal protective equipment (PPE) such as gloves and mouth masks. While these items were crucial in curbing the spread of viruses, their disposal poses significant environmental challenges. Therefore, this study aims to provide deeper insights on the effects on PPE resulting from the exposure in seawater and on the surface of a sandbox, when accidentally disposed. For that purpose different gloves (i.e., nitrile, latex and vinyl) and mouth masks (i.e., FFP2, surgical and generic) were exposed for 18 months to these conditions. Subsequently, samples were collected and analyzed using ambient pressure ionization, more specifically, Direct Analysis in Real-Time coupled to Mass Spectrometry (DART-MS), to assess their chemical composition. Next, Pyrolysis Gas Chromatography coupled to Mass Spectrometry (Py-GC-MS) and attenuated total reflectance infrared spectroscopy were conducted to elucidate potential aging or degradation of the PPE polymer structures.

DART-MS revealed that both masks and gloves exhibited limited degradation. Nevertheless, some interesting patterns emerged. Metal chlorides present in gloves were completely released into the environment, while for example phthalates were prone to oxidation when aged on a sandbox. Regarding mouth masks, generally similar outcomes were discovered, again with more pronounced aging behavior of chemicals in sand-aged samples. Next, Py-GC-MS analysis provided further insights into potential shifts in polymer composition, elucidating whether sea or sand aging can lead to severe degradation of the weathered materials. Lastly, a comparison between the different analysis techniques will be reported.

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